

Mid-term exploitation plan

Deliverable 10.1

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The aim of the SCALIBUR project is to obtain high value products from different types of organic waste, including the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW), wastewater sludge (WWS) and catering and kitchen (HORECA) waste.

Demonstrating that organic waste, if appropriately treated, can turn into a precious raw material source will lead to important environmental benefits, as it addresses two fundamental problems at the same time. On one hand it provides new and more effective waste treatments, reducing the amounts of waste that have to be disposed of or landfilled and, on the other hand, it produces new raw materials from a renewable, local source.

A successful exploitation strategy plays a key role in maximising the impact of the SCALIBUR project. This report will focus on the initial exploitation steps and will lay the ground for the exploitation work that will be done in the following three years.

Each of the 3 pilot cities is highly motivated to exploit the results of SCALIBUR project. This will be done by integrating practices and processes developed in the technical work packages (3-6) into their biowaste management system. **Furthermore, experience gathered through the different work packages will be summarised in best practice fact sheets and policy recommendations to promote uptake in other cities.** The SCALIBUR pilot cities will become case studies and reference cases with national relevance, as they represent an invaluable source of insights in the implementation of circular business models for biowaste. Finally, the current regulations regarding the products and processes developed in SCALIBUR will be analysed and, where appropriate, modification suggestions shall be drafted.

Furthermore, it is expected that the SCALIBUR project will deliver 19 commercially exploitable results: innovative processes and products within the biowaste valorisation value chain. This is an initial assessment and it may be subject to changes during the project life as new unexpected results could be added to the rose of obtained results. A risk analysis highlighted 68 exploitation risks that will have to be managed during the project lifespan. This number is not worrisome as the project consortium includes more than 20 partners and there is a high number of expected exploitable results. Furthermore, the further analysis of the risks highlighted the fact that approximately 40% of these risks are of technical nature while the second largest share of risks (25%) are legislation and regulation related risks. The first category is expected to be solved during the project course, while for the second category it is necessary to build a solid body of

scientific knowledge to inform appropriate changes in relevant laws and regulations. A large number of partners are considering to apply for a patent to protect their findings. This is an extremely encouraging sign for the future exploitation of the SCALIBUR results.

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